

Input from

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About P2GreenN

P2GreenN's ambition is to foster the paradigm shift in our current linearly organised urban blue infrastructure and agricultural nutrient management towards circular clean tech value chains that reduce N and P emissions. P2GreenN aims to develop innovative circular nutrient management systems that

- use wastewater and human urine and faeces from urban areas as a valuable resource,
- recycling N and P via four innovative clean technologies in three pilot regions into bio-based fertilisers,
- which are used for food production in agriculture across Europe, reducing dependencies on current mineral fertilisers.

The nutrients used in P2GreenN fertilisers are the same as in conventional fertilisers used for decades.

Funded by
the European Union

Fertilisers from human excreta and wastewater are as safe as using animal manure as fertilisers for agriculture.

P2GreenN fertilisers reduce the EU's dependence on raw material imports whilst maintaining employment in Europe and supporting the EU's internal market.

P2GreenN solutions contribute to the EU bioeconomy action plan by reducing resource exploitation and promoting waste valorisation, thereby increasing the resilience of the EU's agri-food system.

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Policy Brief

